

Follow-up Frequency and Clinical Outcomes in Patients referred to Physiotherapy for Spine related Orthopaedic Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Background: Musculoskeletal disorders have been a major cause of disability and pain, and the leading cause of disability and pain has been spine related orthopaedic conditions, the symptom being activity limiting low back pain (LBP). Treatment of LBP needs timely follow-up. **Objectives:** Objective of the study was to study the follow-up frequency and clinical outcomes in patients referred to Physiotherapy for spine related orthopaedic conditions. **Material and Methods:** Sixty-eight participants with the average age of 47 years were enrolled in the study based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. An observational study was carried out where they were assessed for pain by Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) Physiotherapeutic exercises and treatment were given to the participants and they were asked to visit for subsequent follow-ups after a 10 day period. Whether they visited for the follow-up was noted. **Results:** Microsoft Excel was used for the data analysis. Findings of the study were analyzed by graphical representation. It was observed that a huge number of patients were lost during the first follow-up and the number reduced even more in the second and third follow-up. **Conclusions:** A smaller number of patients visited for follow-ups and continuation of further management. It was concluded that they prefer pharmaceutical drugs more than regular follow-up. Distance and time could be the factors due to which patients did not attend the consequent follow-ups. Hence if a system is developed for delivering health care at their door-step, patients will benefit from that.

Keywords: Physiotherapy, Follow-up, Low Back Pain, Oswestry Disability Index, Visual Analog Scale

INTRODUCTION

Musculoskeletal disorders have been the leading cause of disability including spine related orthopaedic conditions, the symptom being activity limiting low back pain.(1,2) Up to 30% of consultations in primary care are of patients with some or the other musculoskeletal disorders.1 The lifetime prevalence of Low back pain is 42% worldwide and 66% in Indian population respectively. It continues to be a very common problem globally. With increase in populations, the total number of people with low back pain is likely to increase substantially over the coming years.2,3 Due to this the second-highest reason for

consulting a general medical practitioner (GP) is Low Back Pain.4 Although it is believed that fewer than 40% of patients require an orthopaedic surgical approach.5,6,7 The current health challenge, population is facing difficulties to access to good orthopaedic consultation. The consultation must provide equally effective alternative care for patients who may not require surgical intervention.8 Subsequently in recent years, attention has been shifted to newer models of care such as Physiotherapy Pain Rehabilitation Program (PT-PRP) and Physiotherapist-led (PT-led) orthopaedic triage. PT-

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led approach has been applied primarily in countries such as Australia, Canada, Ireland, UK and Sweden, but not yet in India.^{1,9} This approach involves a physiotherapist (PT) who will assess, diagnose and design a management protocol for patients referred for physiotherapy orthopaedic consultation instead of an Orthopaedic Surgeon.^{10,11} Additionally, patient's perceptions should be taken care of, especially when treatment strategies differ from traditional ways of practice.^{12,13} Patients' outcomes are widely considered as a valid measure of service and quality in health system, as well as clinical efficacy and safety are studied based on patient experiences and responses.¹ Follow-up of treatment remains necessary in any case. Objective for this study was to determine the follow-up frequency and clinical outcomes in patients who were referred for Physiotherapy due to spine related orthopaedic conditions with major complaint of Low Back Pain.

MATERIALS & METHODS

An observational study with prospective study design was carried out in D Y Patil Medical College Hospital and research institute. Convenience sampling was done. Patients of all genders within the age group of 20-75 years were included and patients referred to

Physiotherapy OPD by an Orthopaedic surgeon for spine related low back were included in the study. The study comprised of 68 patients coming for treatment for distant regions, they were advised for timely follow-up. Patients having history of acute spinal trauma or infections and patients not referred to the physiotherapist were excluded from the study. Once recruited into the study, name, age, and gender were recorded on the data collection form. Subjects were assessed for pain by VAS and assessed for disability by ODI. Exercises were then prescribed to the patients based on the assessment. Necessary treatment was also given for the same. After 10 days, participants were asked to visit for follow up. After another 10 days, another follow-up was advised to those who came for the first follow up. The intensity of the exercises was increased throughout the subsequent follow-ups. The number of follow-ups patient completed was noted down and statistical analysis was carried out for the same.

RESULTS

It was seen that a total of Sixty-eight participants participated in the study. Only 12 people came for the first follow-up and 4 people came for the second follow-up.

Graph 1: Graph 1 displays the findings of the study showing loss of follow up.

Thus, the results suggested that treating one area in continuum of muscle-chain has beneficial impact on pain and function of a remote area.

DISCUSSION

The paper aimed to study the follow-up frequency and clinical outcomes in patients referred to physiotherapy for spine related orthopaedic conditions. It was found that very less patients turned up for follow up. These findings are in line with several other studies which state that patients are lost during follow-up. Especially if their area of residence

is away from the hospital. Physiotherapy is mostly provided in secondary and tertiary health care centres, therefore it is not possible for the people residing in remote areas to come and visit at the given time. Moreover, patients have a tendency that when they start feeling little better, they tend to continue with their activities of daily living. When the symptoms of the conditions are settled down, they tend to feel better, but it is obvious that the actual condition is still present as healing requires a huge amount of time and requires a course of treatment or a period of rehabilitation for complete resolution of the actual condition and not just only the symptoms of the condition. Musculoskeletal disorders including Low Back Pain often hampers Activity of Daily living (ADL'S), restricts participation in social events, and reduces Quality of Life due to pain.^{2,9} The fields of advanced and extended scopes of physiotherapy are continually developing, supported by an expanding body of evidence.¹ Spine related orthopaedic conditions do not require surgery unless they are severe that is manifested over a long period of time excluding sudden trauma and around 90 percent of spine conditions are treatable with physiotherapeutic rehabilitation. The aim of a physiotherapist is to rehabilitate the spine when the condition is still in its pre advancement stage, which is before the condition gets severe; it is to be addressed as the age old saying states that 'Prevention is better than cure' Several systematic reviews have been published comparing outcomes of advanced or extended scope of PT-led orthopaedic triage with standard care however, these reviews differ in scope, comparators, and outcomes, includes studies on specific populations, and were published in 2014 and 2015.^{1,14} Furthermore, the reviews concluded that the generally poor methodological quality of included studies, and low certainty of evidence, did not provide evidence for benefits of advanced or extended scope PT-led orthopaedic triage.¹ Physiotherapy is still an evolving branch, and in India, the awareness regarding the same is still developing at a slower pace. Patients often do not visit directly to a therapist, rather they prefer a reference from a physician, especially in areas where there is little or no awareness. Also they prefer to take over the counter analgesics and other pharmaceuticals for pain relief instead of visiting the physician or physiotherapist. Hence, patients need to be educated regarding the importance of rehabilitation

first and then automatically they will consider the importance of follow-ups during the treatment course. Limitations of study included the variety in age distribution. The reason for not attending the follow-up was unclear. Probable factors could be financial status, time and distance, but further research can be required.

CONCLUSION

Overall, this study concludes that a very smaller number of patients visited for follow-ups and continuation of further management. Since majority of the patients were from distant villages around the Kolhapur region, distance and time could be the factors due to which patients did not attend the consequent follow-ups. Also, they prefer short time relief with over the counter drugs more than regular follow ups.

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